

DESCRIPTION OF THE NEIGHBORHOODS OF SAMARKAND IN THE SOURCES OF THE RUSSIAN EMPIRE PERIOD

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Abstract

This article talks about the population, occupation, and ethnic composition of the neighborhoods of the city of Samarkand during the Russian Empire. In addition, information about the national policy of the imperial officials towards the representatives of the indigenous peoples and its consequences has been thoroughly analyzed based on the sources of the imperial era. The level of reliability of the given information was analyzed by means of sources.

Key words: Empire, district, region, source, neighborhood, ethnic composition, nation.

Аннотация

В данной статье рассказывается о населении, роде занятий и этническом составе окрестностей города Самарканда в период Российской империи. Кроме того, на основе источников имперской эпохи тщательно проанализированы сведения о национальной политике имперских чиновников по отношению к представителям коренных народов и ее последствиях. Уровень достоверности предоставленной информации был проанализирован с помощью источников.

Ключевые слова: империя, округ, область, источник, махалла, национальный состав, нация.

Introduction: From the documents and orders drawn up in the early years of the Russian Empire, it is understood that the administration has not yet managed to fully consolidate its management regime, the need to prevent frequent cases of local

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population waiting even for trivial reasons is one of the reasons for preserving the old toponymic neighborhood names. was one. Therefore, in the process of managing the city of Samarkand, local residents will be managed according to the old order. This opinion is proved by the statistical documents of the imperial period compiled for the purpose of studying the city of Samarkand.

The main part: the six gates of the city of Samarkand, which were fully formed by the beginning of the 19th century, and the names of their respective neighborhoods are recorded[1;6]. However, the names of Khoja Ahror, Suzangaron, Paykabad, Qalandarkhana, Yehudyil Mahallasi[1;7] are recorded in the statistical collections of the Russian Empire period. Since 1906, accurate data on the population of five districts of the city of Samarkand has been brought to the Util during the Empire period. According to these data, at the beginning of the 20th century, 9,220 yards and 50,692 people lived in the part of the city of Samarkand inhabited by local residents [1;6]. At the beginning of the 20th century, in the European part of the city of Samarkand, there were 946 courtyards, and their number was 15,974[1;7].

In the middle of the 19th century, there is information about the administrative division of the city of Samarkand based on six gates, and on this basis, the location of neighborhoods and the occupations of their residents. The city of Samarkand, whose population consisted of 25-30 thousand people at the beginning of the 20th century, became a unique metropolis of Central Asia with a population of 66 thousand people. We can explain that the reasons for this are the increase in the number of the local population based on the stable situation, the increase in the number of immigrants, and the strengthening of trade and economic relations based on modern means of production. In the research on the ethnography of the neighborhoods of Samarkand, first of all, there is talk about Uzbeks and Tajiks, a large number of nationalities of the city of Samarkand. Their ethnography, forms of economic management, cultural customs and traditions have been studied.

In the researches of the imperial period, the neighborhood of "Iranians" is mentioned in the city of Samarkand. According to the data, Iranians were at the front of the population in Samarkand. A. D. Grebinkin, an active researcher of ethnography

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of the population of Samarkand of this period, cites his thoughts about the resettlement of Iranians to Samarkand and their neighborhood. "Iran (Kazylbashi) did not come to the city of Samarkand voluntarily. Those who were brought as slaves or born here are also the descendants of former slaves" [6; 111]. Before the invasion of the Iranian king Nadirshah, the Iranians living in the neighborhoods of Samarkand were engaged in crafts and construction. As a result of his invasion, the process of leaving the city of Samarkand began for people whose main faith was Sunni. It was during this period that the Shia Iranians who lived in Samarkand were freed from slavery. done[5;373].

There is also talk about the neighborhoods of Samarkand city during the Zarafshan district and the ethnic Arab neighborhoods that lived there. The places where they live are mainly around the city of Samarkand and Kattakurgan uezd [6; 114]. Arab neighborhoods appeared in the city of Samarkand and its surroundings in the early centuries [3; 180]. In the 17th century, some Arabs from Afghanistan settled in the vicinity of the city of Samarkand, and their main occupation was blacksmithing [3; 185]. In the period of Zarafshan district, information was also given about the life of peoples and clans such as Mazan, Luli, Juchi, Khoja in the city of Samarkand and its surroundings. They could also be found in 32 volosts of Samarand uezd [7; 38]. Since their main occupation is begging (mainly Luli, except for the Khuja clan), they constantly move around without settling down in one place. They mostly lived in separate and small neighborhoods in the city of Samarkand, and were engaged in small handicrafts and partial trade. Grebinkin spoke in detail about the social and economic characteristics of these peoples, and noted that they were given to local residents as barshchina (forced labor) to work, and this situation was especially widespread in the city of Samarkand and Chelak regions. However, during the reign of Amir Nasrullah, this situation was put to an end. That is, their forced labor was ended [6; 115].

During this period, there were Indian and Afghan settlements in the city of Samarkand [4; 16]. Although they are poor nationalities, they have their own villages and played an important role in the social and economic life of Samarkand city. In particular, the Afghan rulers lived in the Kavarzor neighborhood of Samarkand and

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played an important role or were considered the main mediators in the Russian Empire-Great Britain Empire-Afghanistan-Iran relations[4;18]. A.P. In his memoirs, Khoroskhin mentions the Afghans living in Kavarzor neighborhood in Samarkand [10; 66]. In this period, there were 33 caravanserais in the city of Samarkand, with a total of 712 shops. According to the data, 9 of these caravanserais were under the control of Indian citizens [2; 23].

Even after the invasion of the Russian Empire, the neighborhoods of the city of Samarkand were able to save themselves. The main principle that is characteristic only for neighborhoods - that is, not division into neighborhoods by industry, profession, but now division by nationality has come to the fore. In the neighborhoods of Samarkand city, at the time of the establishment of Zarafshan district, there were about 20 It is stated in the sources that 1,000 people live there [6;210], and together with this, all the nationalities and peoples living here are analyzed in detail according to their profession, age, and level of education. In some sources, 30 thousand people live in the city of Samarkand in this period. [2;222].

In the 1891 imperial statistical reference, there are opinions about the structure and population of the city of Samarkand, and the location of its neighborhoods. The part of the city inhabited by the local population was 364 desiatinas. In the city there are 166 large and small streets, and according to the situation in 1891, 11 of them were laid with stone. There were 5154 residential houses in total. The total population is 25,133 people, and Uzbeks, Tajiks, Iranians and other peoples are in the first place in terms of ethnic influence. There was a separate Jewish quarter in the city. The local people named the place where they live Guzari-Juguton[8;21]. Today, this quarter exists around the Registan complex of the city. However, its ethnic composition has changed, and people whose origins go back to the Lulis live there. Sukhareva O.A. and Muqminova R.G. Jews in Samarkand were mainly engaged in painting cubical materials, and they were very skilled in this field [9; 21]. In the middle of the 19th century, the city of Samarkand has been leading as the center of the textile industry since the Middle Ages. It is not surprising that it was the participation of Jews in this process that helped Samarkand to take a leading role in the gas industry.

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Jews in the neighborhoods of Samarkand. Jews lived in separate quarters in the city. But the relationship with the local Muslim population was not bad. The spirit of freedom prevailed in the religious faith of the Jewish community, and necessary conditions were created for them to follow their national religious beliefs. They had their own Synagogue. He could perform religious ceremonies in the synagogue, at home, and in his home. The men wore long cloak-like clothes and large bowl-shaped hats on their heads. Women could walk bareheaded in their quarters. However, when going out to Muslim areas, of course, they wrapped their headscarves [2; 21].

In the data of 1872, an Indian neighborhood of 100 people was mentioned in the city of Samarkand [6; 211]. The Indian citizens who lived here were mainly engaged in trade, usury and medicine, and made their due contribution to the development of the socio-economic life of the city. Afghans, estimated to be about 100 people, also had their own neighborhood in the city of Samarkand [6; 211]. In the sources of this period, it is noted that Afghans engaged in trade and directly or indirectly participated in Afghanistan-India trade. The imperial sources do not provide exact figures on the demographic status of Afghans. Because their main occupation was trade and seasonal work, most of them did not live permanently. The quoted figure does not show the exact number of Afghans living in the city. In fact, there were more than 100 of them.

The Tatars who lived in the city are also mentioned in the sources of the empire period. According to the sources, most of the Tatars who lived in the neighborhoods of Samarkand were learned people [6; 211]. After the city of Samarkand was included in the empire, the Tatars began to mediate the relations between the colonists and the local population. She started working as a secretary in the court, notary office (office, department), preparing information, writing applications, translation services. There was also a small Kyrgyz community in the city of Samarkand [6; 211]. In the sources, their place of residence is not as a separate neighborhood, but in some places in the neighborhoods where Uzbeks and Tajiks live.

Conclusion: the growing influence of the population of Samarkand required the administration of the empire to be managed while preserving the old forms of
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governance. Villages in the cities were again divided into groups and new elders were appointed. The local population was controlled by appointing elders as heads of neighborhoods. The elders delivered the decrees and decisions of the administration to the population, registered the population and involved them in various activities, and led the collection of taxes and fees. Although the small population of the villages did not cause difficulties, the large number of the urban population demanded the introduction or preservation of the local order in the administration.

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